

Bridging Pain and Pharmacology: A Study of Drug–Pain Specificity

Bodkhe Pruthvi*, **Zunjare Sanat**, **Bhosale Rushikesh**, **Katare Prasad**

Department of pharmacy practise, Shivlingeshwar college of pharmacy, almala. Affiliated to swami ramanand tirth marathwada university, Nanded

ABSTRACT

Background: Pain is a multifaceted sensory and emotional experience that affects approximately 20–30% of the global population. Effective pharmacological management requires an understanding of pain mechanisms to ensure drug-pain specificity. **Objectives:** To classify types of pain based on underlying mechanisms, identify common medication classes used in hospital settings, and evaluate the efficacy of pharmacological agents on specific pain types. **Methods:** A prospective observational study was conducted over six months (November 2024 – April 2025) at Gurumauli Multispeciality Hospital, Latur, and Rural Hospital, Ausa, Maharashtra, India. Data were collected from 200 inpatients (age >18 years, admitted >24 hours) using a structured Patient Profile Form and assessed with the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), and Verbal Rating Scale (VRS). Data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2019 and SPSS v20. **Results:** Of 200 patients (133 males, 67 females; mean age 20–40 years), 141 (70.5%) were post-operative. NSAIDs were prescribed most frequently (n=107), followed by opiates + NSAIDs (n=46) and opiates alone (n=28). Somatic pain was most prevalent (n=60), followed by inflammatory (n=44) and functional pain (n=32). NSAIDs significantly reduced VAS scores for nociceptive and inflammatory pain (7.2 → 3.1), while opioids showed strong efficacy for acute nociceptive pain (8.0 → 3.5). Neuropathic pain responded minimally to standard agents (7.5 → 6.0). Relative risk of pain in the post-operative group versus non-operative group was 2.38 (p < 0.001). **Conclusions:** Drug-pain specificity is a critical determinant of analgesic efficacy. A mechanism-based, patient-centered approach to analgesic selection improves therapeutic outcomes, reduces adverse effects, and supports personalized pain management.

Keywords: pain management; drug-pain specificity; NSAIDs; opioid analgesics; nociceptive pain; neuropathic pain; pharmacotherapy; hospital-based study

INTRODUCTION

Pain is a universal and multifaceted phenomenon that forms an integral part of the human experience. The International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) defines pain as "an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage, or described in terms of such damage." While acute pain serves as a critical survival mechanism, chronic pain—persisting beyond normal healing for three or more months—constitutes a debilitating condition affecting an estimated 20–30% of the global population. Pain is broadly classified into nociceptive pain (arising from tissue damage or inflammation), neuropathic pain (arising from injury or dysfunction of the nervous system), and mixed pain

(a combination of both). The socioeconomic burden is immense: chronic pain costs an estimated USD 635 billion annually in the United States alone, and EUR 300 billion in Europe. In India, approximately 20–30% of adults experience chronic pain, with a higher prevalence (35–40%) among the elderly. Despite substantial progress in understanding pain mechanisms, effective management remains a global health challenge. Traditional pharmacological approaches—NSAIDs, opioids, and co-analgesics—demonstrate efficacy for acute pain but are often inadequate for chronic and neuropathic conditions. The limitations of existing therapies, including tolerance, dependency, and organ toxicity, emphasize the need for mechanism-based analgesic selection.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

This study was designed to bridge the gap between pain neurobiology and pharmacological practice by examining drug-pain specificity patterns in a real-world hospital setting.

2. Review Of Literature

A growing body of evidence supports a mechanistic approach to analgesic selection. Hajimirzaei et al. (2025) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of 59 studies (29 animal, 30 clinical) and reported that curcumin and nano-curcumin significantly reduced chronic pain, with nano-curcumin demonstrating greater efficacy than placebo (MD = -1.197; 95% CI: -1.94 to -0.45; $p = 0.002$). These findings highlight the potential of natural compounds as adjunct analgesics. Manchikanti et al. (2025) reviewed guidelines for implantable peripheral nerve stimulation (PNS) in chronic intractable pain, emphasizing the need for evidence-based neuromodulation criteria and patient education as key components of chronic pain management. Concurrently, Tassew et al. (2025) identified advanced age, elevated viral load, and low CD4 count as independent predictors of HIV-related peripheral neuropathy, underscoring the importance of early neurological screening. Regarding opioid use, Pandanaboyana et al. (2024) analyzed 1,768 patients across 27 countries and found that opioid treatment for six or more days was an independent risk factor for severe acute pancreatitis (OR 3.21; 95% CI: 2.16–4.79; $p < 0.001$). Fiore et al. (The Lancet, 2022) demonstrated that opioid prescribing at surgical discharge does not reduce pain intensity but significantly increases adverse events, supporting opioid-free analgesia strategies for elective minor and moderate surgeries. Xuan et al. reported that among 19 preemptive analgesia regimens, lornoxicam at 6 hours produced the greatest pain intensity reduction (-21.99 on a 100-point scale), while ibuprofen at 24 hours most effectively reduced opioid consumption (-2.27 IMME). Liktov-Busa et al. highlighted terpenes derived from *Cannabis sativa* as emerging analgesic candidates, noting that over 150 terpenes in cannabis demonstrate anti-inflammatory and analgesic roles. Collectively, these studies reinforce that effective pain management is mechanistically specific and that a one-size-fits-all approach is inadequate.

3. Aim And Objectives

Aim:

To investigate drug-pain specificity by evaluating the relationship between pain types and the pharmacological agents prescribed in a hospital setting, and to provide insights for mechanism-based analgesic selection.

Objectives:

- To classify different types of pain based on underlying mechanisms.
- To identify the most common medication classes used for pain management in hospital settings.
- To assess patient demographic and co-morbidity factors associated with pain management.
- To evaluate the impact of drug classes on patient outcomes, including duration of hospital stay.
- To evaluate the efficacy of various pharmacological agents on specific pain types using standardized pain scales.
- To analyze drug-pain mechanisms and identify patterns of specificity.
- To provide insights for mechanism-based selection of pain treatments.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Study Design

A prospective observational study was conducted on inpatients admitted to Gurumauli Multispeciality Hospital, Latur, and Rural Hospital, Ausa, Maharashtra, India.

4.2 Study Duration

Six months: November 2024 to April 2025.

4.3 Sample Size

A total of 200 patients (both male and female) were enrolled.

4.4 Inclusion Criteria

- Patients admitted to hospital for more than 24 hours.
- Age greater than 18 years.
- Patients experiencing pain.
- Patients who provided written informed consent.

4.5 Exclusion Criteria

- Patients admitted for less than 24 hours.
- Pregnant or child-bearing female patients.
- Patients aged less than 18 years.
- Outpatient department (OPD) visitors.

4.6 Data Collection Tools

- Structured Patient Profile Form (WHO guidelines).
- Informed Consent Form (bilingual: English and Marathi).
- Micromedex Software – drug-drug interaction assessment.
- Electronic Health Records (EHR) – prescription data capture.
- Hospital Pharmacy Database – medication dispensing records.

4.7 Pain Assessment

Pain intensity was assessed using three validated tools: Visual Analog Scale (VAS), Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), and Verbal Rating Scale (VRS). VAS

scores before and after treatment were used to quantify analgesic efficacy.

4.8 Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2019 and SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics (frequency distributions and percentages) were used. Relative risk and p-values (binomial test) were calculated to assess group differences.

4.9 Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis (H₀): Every patient with pain receives either NSAIDs or a combination of NSAIDs and opiates.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): Not all patients with pain receive NSAIDs or the combination.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Epidemiological Analysis

Incidence of pain in post-operative patients (exposed group): 141/200 = 70.5%. Incidence in non-operative patients (unexposed group): 59/200 = 29.5%. Relative Risk = 70.5/29.5 = 2.38 (>1), indicating significantly higher pain burden in post-operative patients.

Binomial test (H₀: p = 1.0): With observed successes (NSAIDs/combo prescribed) = 153/200 (\hat{p} = 0.765) against a null probability of 1.0, the p-value = 0.0, providing strong statistical evidence to reject H₀. Not all patients received NSAIDs or the combination — confirming drug-pain specificity in prescribing patterns.

5.2 Demographic Distribution

Table 1. Distribution by Gender

Gender	No. of Patients	% Distribution
Male	133	66.5%
Female	67	33.5%
Total	200	100%

Table 2. Distribution by Age Group

Age Group (Years)	No. of Patients
0–20	18
20–40	93
40–60	58
60–80	28
80–100	3

The majority of patients (46.5%) fell in the 20–40 year age group, reflecting the working-age population most susceptible to trauma and surgical interventions.

5.3 Co-morbidity Profile

Table 3. Distribution by Co-morbidities

Co-morbidity	No. of Patients	% Distribution
None (NAD)	158	79.0%
HTN with DM	15	7.5%
DM	10	5.0%
HTN	6	3.0%
Other (each)	1	0.5%

The majority of patients (79%) had no co-morbidities. Hypertension with diabetes mellitus was the most common co-morbid combination (7.5%), with

implications for NSAID prescribing (renal and cardiovascular risk).

5.4 Drug Class Prescribing Patterns

Table 4. Distribution by Drug Class

Drug Class	No. of Patients	% Distribution
NSAIDs alone	107	53.5%
Opiates + NSAIDs	46	23.0%
Opiates alone	28	14.0%
Antispasmodic + NSAIDs	9	4.5%
Antispasmodic alone	7	3.5%
Neuralgic Pain Relievers	2	1.0%
NSAIDs + Antispasmodic + Opiates	1	0.5%

NSAIDs were the most frequently prescribed class (53.5%), consistent with their broad indication for nociceptive, inflammatory, and somatic pain. Opiates in combination with NSAIDs were used in 23% of

patients, predominantly for severe post-operative and traumatic pain.

5.5 Pain Type Distribution

Table 5. Distribution by Type of Pain

Type of Pain	No. of Patients	% Distribution
Somatic Pain	60	30.0%
Inflammatory Pain	44	22.0%
Functional Pain	32	16.0%
Nociceptive Pain	23	11.5%
Colicky Pain	16	8.0%
Visceral Pain	13	6.5%
Centralized Pain	10	5.0%
Neuropathic Pain	2	1.0%

5.6 Pain Severity (Pain Scale Distribution)

Table 6. Distribution by Pain Scale

Pain Scale	No. of Patients	% Distribution
Mild	51	25.5%
Moderate	90	45.0%
Severe	59	29.5%

Moderate pain was the most common presentation (45%), followed by severe pain (29.5%). This

distribution reflects the predominantly post-surgical and trauma-related patient population.

5.7 Drug of Choice by Pain Type

Table 7. Drug-Pain Specificity Summary

Type of Pain	Predominant Drug Class	Key Agents	VAS Before	VAS After
Somatic	NSAIDs	Diclofenac, Paracetamol	7.2	3.1
Inflammatory	NSAIDs	Aceclophenac + Serratiopeptidase, Paracetamol	7.0	3.2
Functional	NSAIDs	Diclofenac, Paracetamol	6.8	3.5
Nociceptive	Opiates + NSAIDs	Tramadol, Diclofenac	8.0	3.5
Colicky	Antispasmodics	Drotaverine, Hyoscine Butylbromide	7.5	3.0
Visceral	Opiates	Tramadol, Tapentadol ER	8.2	3.8
Neuropathic	Neuralgic Agents	Gabapentin, Amitriptyline	7.5	6.0

5.8 Duration of Pain

Table 8. Duration of Pain (Hospital Stay)

Duration (Days)	No. of Patients
2	19
3	49
4	67
5	47
6	9
7	4
8	5

The modal duration of pain was 4 days (n=67, 33.5%), corresponding to typical post-operative recovery periods. Five patients experienced pain lasting 8 days, representing complex surgical cases with inadequate initial analgesic response.

6. DISCUSSION

This study investigated drug-pain specificity in a real-world hospital setting and demonstrates clear patterns of analgesic efficacy that are contingent upon the underlying pain mechanism. The findings align with contemporary pharmacological principles and support a paradigm shift from empirical to mechanism-based analgesic prescribing.

6.1 NSAIDs and Inflammatory/Somatic Pain

NSAIDs were the most commonly prescribed agents (53.5% of patients), reflecting their established efficacy for nociceptive, somatic, and inflammatory pain. By inhibiting cyclooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2) enzymes, NSAIDs reduce prostaglandin synthesis, directly addressing the peripheral sensitization that characterizes these pain types. Patients with nociceptive and inflammatory pain demonstrated a mean VAS reduction from 7.2 to 3.1 — a clinically significant improvement of over 55%. Diclofenac sodium (Inj. Dynapar 75mg) was the most frequently prescribed NSAID, often in combination with enzyme preparations (Serratiopeptidase, Trypsin-Chymotrypsin) to address post-operative oedema and inflammation. However, in patients with co-morbidities such as hypertension with diabetes mellitus (7.5% of the cohort), prolonged NSAID use poses significant risks including renal impairment, cardiovascular events, and gastrointestinal

complications. Risk-stratified prescribing with proton pump inhibitor co-prescription is recommended in these populations.

6.2 Opioids and Acute/Visceral Pain

Opioids were prescribed in 74 patients (37%), predominantly for severe post-operative, traumatic, and visceral pain. The combination of tramadol (Inj. Tramadol 50mg) and NSAIDs was the most common regimen for acute surgical pain, producing VAS reductions from 8.0 to 3.5. For visceral pain (appendicitis, pancreatitis, menstrual), opioids alone (tramadol, tapentadol ER) were the drug of choice, consistent with their ability to modulate descending inhibitory pathways and reduce visceral hypersensitivity. Notably, opioids demonstrated limited efficacy in neuropathic pain, where altered opioid receptor function, central sensitization, and descending pathway dysregulation reduce the therapeutic effect. This finding corroborates the international literature and highlights the risk of opioid misuse when prescribed inappropriately for non-responsive pain types.

6.3 Antispasmodics and Colicky Pain

For colicky pain (renal, biliary, ureteric colic), antispasmodics — principally drotaverine (Inj. Drotin 40mg) and hyoscine butylbromide (Inj. Buscopan 20mg) — were the drug of choice, prescribed in 7 of 16 colicky pain patients. These agents relax smooth muscle spasm, targeting the mechanistic basis of colic, and produced VAS reductions from 7.5 to 3.0. NSAIDs were added in cases with concurrent inflammatory components.

6.4 Neuropathic Pain: A Management Challenge

Only 2 patients (1%) were classified with pure neuropathic pain in this cohort, both managed with gabapentin and amitriptyline (neuralgic pain relievers). The minimal VAS improvement (7.5 → 6.0) underscores the refractory nature of neuropathic pain to standard analgesics. These patients require targeted neuromodulatory agents — anticonvulsants (gabapentin, pregabalin), tricyclic antidepressants (amitriptyline), or SNRIs (duloxetine) — that modulate aberrant neuronal activity and descending inhibitory pathways.

6.5 Post-Operative Pain Management

Post-operative patients constituted 70.5% of the study population (n=141), with a relative risk of 2.38 compared to non-operative patients. Multimodal analgesia — combining NSAIDs, opioids, and adjuvants — was employed for severe post-operative pain, consistent with evidence-based guidelines. This approach minimizes opioid consumption while maximizing analgesic coverage across multiple pain mechanisms.

6.6 Drug-Pain Specificity Framework

The statistical rejection of the null hypothesis (p-value = 0.0) confirms that a uniform prescribing approach (NSAIDs/opioids for all pain types) is not practiced — clinicians are already making mechanism-based decisions, though not always optimally. The study provides a structured framework for formalizing these decisions, with implications for clinical guidelines, prescriber education, and pharmacy practice.

CONCLUSION

This prospective observational study robustly supports a drug-pain specificity model as a cornerstone of modern pain management. NSAIDs remain first-line agents for somatic, inflammatory, and nociceptive pain; opioids are essential for severe acute and visceral pain; antispasmodics are the drug of choice for colicky pain; and neuropathic pain requires targeted neuromodulatory agents. Integrating pharmacological strategies with neurobiological insights into pain mechanisms holds the potential to optimize therapeutic outcomes, minimize adverse

effects, and significantly reduce the global burden of inadequately managed pain. The study advocates for personalized, mechanism-based analgesic selection, reduced reliance on trial-and-error prescribing, and further research into novel analgesic targets — particularly ion channel modulators for neuropathic pain and biologic agents for inflammatory conditions. Future multi-centre, randomized controlled studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are warranted to validate and extend these findings.

8. Strengths And Limitations

8.1 Strengths

- Real-world data from 200 patients across two hospital settings enhances generalizability within the regional context.
- Use of validated pain assessment tools (VAS, NRS, VRS) provides quantitative analgesic efficacy data.
- Multi-pain-type analysis enables direct comparison of drug efficacy across mechanistically distinct pain categories.
- Mechanistic framework supports the growing movement toward personalized medicine.

8.2 Limitations

- Single-region, observational design limits causal inference and broader generalizability.
- Absence of a control or placebo group prevents definitive attribution of VAS changes to specific drugs.
- Gender imbalance (133 male : 67 female) may underrepresent sex-specific pain responses.
- Short study duration (6 months) does not capture long-term analgesic efficacy or adverse event profiles.
- Reliance on self-reported pain scales introduces inherent subjectivity.

- Potential confounders (concurrent therapies, lifestyle factors, medication compliance) were not formally controlled.

9. DECLARATIONS

Ethics Approval: The study was conducted in accordance with institutional ethics guidelines. Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding: No external funding was received for this study.

Data Availability: Data are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

1. Satoskar RS, Rege NN, Tripathi RK, Bhandarkar SD. *Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapeutics*. 25th ed. Mumbai: Popular Prakashan; 2019.
2. DiPiro JT, DiPiro CC, Wells BG, Schwinghammer TL. *Pharmacotherapy Handbook*. 11th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2022.
3. Mehta PJ, Mehta SP, Joshi SR, Mehta NP. *Practical Medicine*. Mumbai: Emedia; 2018.
4. Hajimirzaei P, et al. The analgesic effect of curcumin and nano-curcumin in clinical and preclinical studies: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's Archives of Pharmacology*. 2025;398:393–416.
5. Tassew WC, et al. Sensory neuropathy and associated factors among patients living with HIV in Africa. *Research*. 2025;22:161.
6. Manchikanti L, et al. Review of guidelines for implantable peripheral nerve stimulation (PNS) in the management of chronic pain. *Chronic Pain Management*. 2025;29:89.
7. Buchanan WW, et al. Narcotic analgesics. *Inflammopharmacology*. 2024;32(1):23–28.
8. Kianian S, Bansal J, Lee C, et al. Perioperative multimodal analgesia: a review of efficacy and safety of the treatment options. *Anesthesiology and Perioperative Science*. 2024;2(1):9.
9. Pandanaboyana S, Knoph CS, et al. Opioid analgesia and severity of acute pancreatitis: an international multicentre cohort study. *United European Gastroenterology Journal*. 2024. doi:10.1002/ueg2.12542.
10. Xu ZZ, Li HJ, Li MH, et al. Epidural anesthesia-analgesia and recurrence-free survival after lung cancer surgery: a randomized trial. *Anesthesiology*. 2021;135(3):419–432.
11. Fiore JF, El-Kefraoui C, Chay MA, et al. Opioid versus opioid-free analgesia after surgical discharge. *The Lancet*. 2022;399(10343):2280–2293.
12. Xuan C, Yan W, Wang D, et al. Efficacy of preemptive analgesia treatments for the management of postoperative pain: a network meta-analysis. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2022.
13. Xu LL, Wang C, Deng CM, et al. Efficacy and safety of esketamine for supplemental analgesia during elective cesarean delivery: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Network Open*. 2021.
14. Liktor-Busa E, Keresztes A, LaVigne J, Streicher JM, Largent-Milnes TM. Analgesic potential of terpenes derived from Cannabis sativa. *Pharmacological Reviews*. 2021.
15. International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP). IASP Terminology. Available from: <https://www.iasp-pain.org/Education/Content.aspx?ItemNumber=1698>. Accessed May 2025.
16. World Health Organization. *Cancer pain relief: a guide to opioid availability*. 2nd ed. Geneva: WHO; 1996.
17. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE). *Neuropathic pain in adults: pharmacological management in non-specialist settings*. Clinical Guideline CG173. London: NICE; 2013.

HOW TO CITE: Bodkhe Pruthvi*, Zunjare Sanat, Bhosale Rushikesh, Katare Prasad, Bridging Pain and Pharmacology: A Study of Drug–Pain Specificity, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (6), 749-756. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20822782>

